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On the Ontology of Multidisciplinary Epistemic Groups

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Multidisciplinary research teams in academia constitute *plural subjects*. This means research teams that do not share methodological standards – which I call *multidisciplinary epistemic groups* – exist as entities that are ontologically distinct from their individual members. I argue for this account by drawing on Gilbert (1989). On the one hand, plural subjects are identifiable as agents that are not reducible to their individual members. This is the case in academia, where scientists ascribe trust to research teams rather than each member of those teams (Wilholt, 2016). On the other hand, plural subjects make judgements that are also irreducible to the judgements of their members. In the case of multidisciplinary epistemic groups, their scientific conclusions are not reducible to the premises of their individual members (Dang, 2019). Drawing on Paternotte (2020), I call this the *ontological maximalism* account of multidisciplinary epistemic groups.

However, the academic context in which multidisciplinary epistemic groups operate entails adhering to certain academic norms. I argue that academic norms influence individualistic desires. The importance of individuals' goals problematises the maximalist account. On the one hand, the argument for plural subjects is for ontologically irreducible entities – there is no account of individualistic desires. On the other hand, academic norms challenge the very efficacy of multidisciplinary in academia. I expand specifically on this second problem, arguing that philosophical theories about multidisciplinary epistemic groups must make room for the conflicting academic context in which they operate.

The complexity multidisciplinary epistemic groups face can be studied through a two-pronged description of the culture of “publish-or-perish”. Firstly, scientists are credited within delineated disciplinary communities. This is challenging for individuals working across disciplines. For example, a historian working on a digital humanities project with computer scientists might not be given due credit by either historians – who do not understand the project's methods – and/or computer scientists – who do not understand the historian's input. The way scientific disciplines are defined incentivises individuals to work within research disciplines (Lee, 2020). On the other hand, there is a cost to developing one's breadth of knowledge to meaningfully engage with peers from other disciplines. Researchers in academia are not effectively encouraged to cross epistemic boundaries (Poteete et al., 2010).

Academic norms entail challenges for multidisciplinary epistemic groups. Yet, multidisciplinary is on the rise. An ontological account of these groups must accommodate for the challenges they face. I argue we can account

for these challenges with Bratman's (2014) individualistic theory of joint action. In short, Bratman provides a conceptual framework that helps make sense of divergent plans within groups. He suggests a "social glue" constituted by *social rationality norms*: social agglomeration, social consistency and coherence, and social stability. These social norms enable individuals' preferences to mesh together and form congruent *shared intentions*. I show that Bratman's framework is helpful but misses a crucial aspect: he does not focus on groups that *do not* share background assumptions. Meanwhile, multidisciplinary epistemic groups, by definition, do not share methodological standards broadly construed. Hence, we need something additional to account for ontologically irreducible research teams in academia.

I propose that the additional resource needed to make sense of multidisciplinary is *social epistemic humility*. Social epistemic humility helps multidisciplinary epistemic groups overcome some of the challenges posed by academic norms. It is about being aware of the limitations of one's field of specialisation. By working on projects with colleagues from other disciplines, social epistemic humility helps individuals ascribe trust to colleagues from other disciplines to fill in the gaps their own disciplines are not ready to handle. I argue that social epistemic humility is one epistemic virtue that can promote epistemic trust amongst members of multidisciplinary epistemic groups.

The essay proceeds as follows. In section one, I outline developments in the social epistemology of science. With this, I locate my thesis in the philosophy of interdisciplinarity, and provide a definition for *multidisciplinarity*. In section two, I argue for multidisciplinary epistemic groups as meeting the requisites for Gilbert's *plural subjects*. In section three, I introduce some academic norms that emphasise the importance of individuals' incentives within academia. In section four, I propose that Bratman's theory of joint action can help make sense of individualistic desires in ontologically irreducible groups. I find that Bratman's theory does not account for groups that do not share background assumptions. Thus, in section five, I argue for a further tool for multidisciplinary epistemic groups to form some "social glue" that helps them overcome the challenges posed by academic norms. I argue that *social epistemic humility* promotes epistemic trust in a way that is conducive to this objective. Finally, I introduce and respond to two objections to my thesis.

1. NAVIGATING THE LITERATURE

In this section, I introduce the two main philosophical sub-fields that motivate this essay: social epistemology of science, and joint action theory. I begin by outlining the development of philosophical inquiry into the social nature of science. With this, I will argue for the particular sense in which I speak of *multidisciplinarity*. I then introduce joint action theory, which will be drawn on more explicitly throughout the essay.

1.1. SOCIALISING SCIENCE

I will speak of the social epistemology of science to refer to the study of knowledge-production *qua* social endeavour. This field of work can be traced to at least as far back as John Stuart Mill's essay *On Liberty* (Longino, 2019). Mill (1859) identifies the need for dialogue in the pursuit of justifying beliefs and reaching consensus as to what is "true". Agreeing upon what is true as a collective process mitigates individuals' fallibility and cognitive limitations. This framing of individuals' fallibility would inspire future work in the social epistemology of science. For example, consider Karl Popper's theory of *falsificationism*, which holds that science proceeds by identifying the inaccuracies of contemporary scientific theories (Popper, 1962 [1968]). In a practical sense, this means scientists must demonstrate inadequacies in the conceptual framework or observations of their predecessors and peers (Longino, 2019). As with Mill, the case is that science proceeds through checks and balances developed through a social enterprise.

The social nature of knowledge-production has become more salient in recent decades. This is evidenced by growing research team sizes, and scientific projects increasingly drawing on different disciplines (see Van Noorden, 2015; Earnshaw, 2020). This leaves room for philosophers to investigate the nature of *interdisciplinarity*. Mäki (2016) has argued for the "philosophy of interdisciplinarity" as a useful field of inquiry. Mäki's conception of a philosophy of interdisciplinarity is purposefully broad, touching on numerous issues studied by philosophy of science: from the (dis)unity of science to questions of incommensurability, and the study of the relationship between the social sciences and the natural sciences (*ibid.*: 337). Furthermore, Mäki identifies two "kinds of information" that philosophy of interdisciplinarity can acquire (*ibid.*: 335-336). On the one hand, such studies can identify the similarities and differences between two or more disciplines. On the other hand, such studies can produce "information [...] about what happens (or fails to happen) when two or

more disciplines are brought in contact with one another" (*ibid.*: 337). I will work on the latter endeavour. I study what happens when researchers from diverse disciplines convene in multidisciplinary epistemic groups (MEGs, hereafter).¹ Moreover, I do not focus on any particular combination of disciplines (say, economists working with historians, or physicists with archaeologists).

To clarify, I will speak of *multidisciplinarity* in the following sense:

Multidisciplinarity is present in research teams where there is heterogeneity of methodological standards by virtue of team members drawing on distinct disciplines.

This definition is adapted from Jantsch and Piaget's "three levels of interdisciplinarity" (OECD, 1972). *Multidisciplinarity* is the least demanding of the three levels on the relationships forged between disciplines. It is less demanding than "interdisciplinarity"; and "interdisciplinarity" is less demanding than "transdisciplinarity" (*ibid.*: 133-136).² This is because multidisciplinary is present where there is "persistent heterogeneity of information used" in research teams, albeit sharing "interdisciplinary objectives" (*ibid.*: 133).

However, Jantsch and Piaget's "heterogeneity of information" is too narrow a term for the study of MEGs. By speaking of "heterogeneity of methodological standards", I hope to capture both differing sources of information *and* differing analytical tools. This clarifies the sense in which multidisciplinary is "less demanding" than the other two levels: members in MEGs do not part from a place of consensus, and they needn't be capable of fully engaging with one another's discipline throughout a project.

¹ On pronunciation: "MEG" is an acronym, thus pronounced /mæg/, like the name "Meg" or the abbreviation of "megabyte".

² It should be noted that there is little consensus about the precise difference between *interdisciplinarity* and *transdisciplinarity* (see Lawrence, 2010), which I take to be a further argument for the intervention of philosophers of interdisciplinarity.

1.2. JOINT ACTION THEORY

Having defined multidisciplinary in the previous section, I am interested in how theories of social groups might be deployed to explain MEGs. I develop an account based on the philosophical tradition of joint action theory. Very roughly, we can see joint action as those actions that involve various agents under certain conditions.

Consider Bratman's (1993) study of a musical duet wherein two people successfully sing together. Joint action theory is about identifying the conditions that allow for such a duet to perform together. Questions in joint action theory ask whether the two singers share rules that guide them (perhaps they sing in a certain key), share intentions (maybe to amaze an audience), share understandings of one another's intentions (make their aims *common knowledge*), and so on.

I draw on two prominent and opposing views in joint action theory. Firstly, I argue that Gilbert's *ontological maximalism* solves part of the question of MEGs. Secondly, I argue that Bratman's deeper analysis of the role of individuals in groups provides answers to some challenges Gilbert's framework cannot account for.

Whilst Bratman and Gilbert's theories are in opposition, both describe "minimalist" characterisations of "simple, intuitive cases" (Paternotte, 2020: 42). Amongst other examples they describe are people walking together and poetry reading clubs. These are not *prima facie* large nor complex. In the meantime, MEGs are intuitively complex. Thus, as I argue for their usefulness in describing MEGs, I will also provide caveats. This will be facilitated by my drawing on philosophy and sociology of science, as mentioned above.

Having identified the two main bodies of literature this essay builds on, I turn to its first thesis: Gilbert's *plural subjects* provide a useful framework for thinking about MEGs. I make this case by drawing on Wilholt's (2016) theory of trust-attribution to research groups, and Dang's (2019) theory of group-level judgements in science.

2. GILBERTIAN MEGS

In this section, I introduce Gilbert's approach to joint action theory. Her account provides two arguments for *ontological maximalism*, the view that groups constitute *plural subjects* that are ontologically distinct from their members. On the one hand, groups constitute plural subjects when identified as agents. On the other hand,

groups exist *qua* plural subjects by making judgements that are not reducible to their members'. I argue that these two conclusions hold in the case of MEGs by drawing on Wilholt (2016) and Dang (2019), respectively.

2.1. ONTOLOGICAL MAXIMALISM

Gilbert (1989) argues that certain social groups form *plural subjects*. Two conditions are necessary to grant a social group the status of plural subject: (i) *joint commitment* and (ii) said joint commitment being *common knowledge*. I briefly introduce the two conditions that I later show are present in the case of MEGs.

Joint commitment amounts to individuals of a group *sharing* in some commitment to act and believe *qua* social group. What allows group members to *share* in this commitment is that it is *common knowledge* amongst group members that peers have said commitment. Expressing the joint commitment in some way facilitates its becoming common knowledge. Let us consider an example to better understand what is going on.

Gilbert (1990) suggests *walking together* as a paradigmatic example of forming a plural subject that meets both conditions: its members (i) demonstrate joint commitment and (ii) it is common knowledge that they share this joint commitment. When two people walk together side by side and at the same pace, they can show that each individual is committed to the goal of walking in one another's company. In sharing this commitment to do something *as a group*, what results is a plural subject.

Furthermore, when a social group constitutes a plural subject, Gilbert argues that a special sense of the word "we" can be employed. Gilbert calls this *we**. *We** refers to "a set of people, each of whom shares with oneself in some action, belief, attitude, or other such attribute" (*ibid.*: 201). Those who form a plural subject share some set of beliefs (or other) with one another, and can acknowledge this by speaking in terms of *we**. In the example of walking together, they can say "shall *we** stop here?" or "shall *we** go through the woods?" (8).

It is worth noting that *we** needn't be uttered as such, but its sense must be present. That is, for there to be a plural subject, its members must share in some set of beliefs (or other) – in our example, the individuals share in the action of walking together. Furthermore, joint commitment must be *common knowledge*. Whichever way the joint commitment is expressed, it must be known to fellow group members (i) that it is the case that all other group members share in such commitment, (ii) that each group member is aware of fellow group members' commitment, and (iii) that this form of common knowledge is shared amongst the group in what regards their

joint commitment (*ibid.*). With this, a plural subject exists when the members of a group have common knowledge of each other's joint commitment and, therefore, can speak of *we**.

In the case of MEGs, I drop the *we**-condition for identifying MEGs as plural subjects. In the following section, I argue that members of MEGs share in joint commitment to follow irreducibly social norms. I do not assume that MEGs' members must identify themselves as *we**. However, MEGs *are* identified as plural subjects by scientific communities.

2.2. TRUSTING MEGS

Consider how we ascribe agency to organisations in ordinary conversation. I might claim "the organisation *X*'s actions are detrimental to the environment", that "I do not trust *X*" and, therefore, "*X* doesn't deserve my money" (see List & Pettit, 2011; Tollefsen, 2015). Here, I am ascribing agency to a group in the sense that the group is capable of conducting itself. I am assuming *X* makes decisions that are detrimental to the environment and that my response (to no longer buy from them) will impact *X*. At no moment do I call on individual decision-makers within *X*. This rationale is present in science, where – as Wilholt (2016) argues – peers trust scientific teams without referring to the trustworthiness of said teams' individual members.

Beliefs are held by subjects. Trust in those beliefs depends on the trustworthiness of the subjects that hold them. In what follows, I argue that those subjects can be MEGs. To argue for a Gilbertian notion of MEGs as plural subjects, I draw on Wilholt (2016).

Wilholt argues that scientists trust research groups without needing to trust each individual who forms them. This is because the trustworthiness of research groups results from their following *methodological standards*. Methodological standards are sets of rules or guidelines to ensure the adequacy of research. They are a social convention in the sense of emerging from the social practice of research, rather than any "analytical truth", so to speak. An example methodological standard is holding 0.05 as the p-value, the highest acceptable significance level in significance tests. In many fields that draw on statistical analyses, a p-value of up to 0.05 will be considered a useful result for the advancement of scientific knowledge. Other such methodological standards might be the use of randomised clinical trials in the case of medicine. Following these standards means researchers can ascribe *epistemic trust*; both the research groups and their scientific claims are deemed

trustworthy. There is no need to probe the research group's members for their trustworthiness any further if they follow the methodological standards of their relevant discipline.

Underlying Wilholt's claim about trust ascription is an argument about efficiency: it is more efficient to trust groups than to probe the trustworthiness of each of their members. This demonstrates the "economic" value of considering MEGs to be trustworthy *qua* plural subjects. In other words, ontological maximalism serves a purpose for scientific community when it comes to research groups.

However, Wilholt's argument for ontological maximalism relies on shared methodological standards. In the meantime, MEGs *do not* have such shared standards. I tackle this challenge in the following section.

2.3. THE PROBLEM OF METHODOLOGICAL STANDARDS

MEGs do not have shared standards, and this undermines the usefulness of Wilholt's account in the case of MEGs. Here, I argue that this is not problematic.

One strategy to adapt Wilholt's account to the context of MEGs might be to use a weaker notion of "methodological standards". Consider some of the methodological standards he mentions: the use of positive control groups in the case of animal testing, or the registration of clinical trials in public repositories in biomedical research (*ibid.*: 222). These are field-specific cases of methodological standards. They will not work in multidisciplinary enterprises. Therefore, we need a weaker form of such standards. The case of the p-value discussed above is also provided by Wilholt and can be shared by many more fields. Indeed, significance tests can be employed in any scientific project that involves some statistical analysis. However, there is still a concern in the context of MEGs that this specific standard is not relevant to all the fields that come into contact. Consider the case of a digital humanities project bringing together computer scientists and historians. Whilst the former might be accustomed to analysing statistical data, the latter may not employ significance tests whatsoever.³ What we are after is a standard that is relevant to *all* disciplines to be useful to describe *all* MEGs. This is unlikely to exist, so the strategy to find a weaker notion of methodological standard is infeasible.

³ I hope this example is not offensive to historians who enjoy a good quantitative analysis.

The strategy I follow is to focus not on methodological standards *per se*, but on their “irreducibly social nature”. As Wilholt explains “[methodological standards] are conventional in character and, thus, irreducibly social” (*ibid.*: 223). So, what we need is a social convention that is present across research fields. This is a straightforward task thanks to our fixing the institutional context of MEGs: academia. Indeed, the institution of academia is constituted by a series of social conventions.⁴ With MEGs enacting these social conventions, we needn’t rely on Wilholt’s talk of methodological standards, but his argument that social conventions render research groups ontologically maximal. In other words, what enables MEGs to be trusted *qua* plural subjects is their members’ joint commitment to following academic norms.

2.4. EMBRACING EPISTEMIC DIVERSITY

We have so far seen that, conforming to social conventions, MEGs become ontologically distinct from their members. In this section, I turn to Dang (2019) to argue that MEGs also make judgements *qua* plural subjects. Whilst Wilholt assumes shared methodological standards, Dang does no such thing. Dang holds that diversity in scientific practice is a matter of fact. This is trivially the case for MEGs, where *epistemic diversity* is a constitutive factor. Epistemic diversity is present where researchers from different disciplines follow different methodologies when approaching scientific questions.

Disagreements about methodology are to be expected. The question then rises: how can MEGs agree on their collaborations’ outputs? To respond to this, Dang distinguishes between conclusions *P* and its premises or reasons *R*. Given the diversity in MEGs and the inevitability of disagreement, Dang argues for a model of collective justification whereby *P* needn’t require that all members of the collaboration agree with *P* but that

⁴ This will be expanded on in §3.1. *Academic Norms*.

the group reach consensus on P . This means that any disagreement over P needs justifying. In the meantime, reasons R needn't be shared by collaborators. This allows for a lack of shared methodological standards.⁵

Consider McGillivray et al. (2019). In their research, they sought to apply computational models to track the evolution of the meaning of words in Ancient Greek texts throughout time. This required rather distinct sets of skills and knowledge. We can point to these by identifying three stages in the project. Firstly, there was the need to identify a corpus of Ancient Greek texts for their semantic analysis. This was *The Diorisis Ancient Greek Corpus* (Vatri & McGillivray, 2018). Secondly, the team's classicists annotated a selection of sentences that contained three polysemous lemmas (*harmonia*, *mus* and *kosmos*) used frequently throughout the corpus. The resulting dataset can be found in McGillivray (2019). Finally, the team provide an analysis of the application of two computational models to the annotated texts. These are SCAN (Frerman & Lapata, 2016), which applies a Bayesian model to the case of semantic change in English since the eighteenth century; and GASC (Perrone et al., 2019), which seeks to help with the scaling up of pattern-detection in the semantic evolution of the Ancient Greek lexicon.

McGillivray et al. (2019) present a co-dependence between two groups of field experts – let us call them “classicists” and “computer scientists”. Whilst it is true that both groups would reach consensus regarding the final outcome of the project – the foundation for a computational model to track the meaning of words in Ancient Greek —, there is no requirement for both to actively engage with one another's methods and premises. Consider the difference between one's methodology and the other's, as well as the specific expertise required at each stage. It is not feasible to expect that each group – let alone each researcher – comprehend all the work conducted by the other. To this effect, we have an account of scientific collaboration without shared methodological standards. What's more, we have some output P made by a group, and some premises R held

⁵ Recall Jantsch and Piaget's notion of *multidisciplinarity* as the lowest rung in a hierarchy of types of interdisciplinarity (§1.1.). Dang's inclusive notion of agreeing on outputs P without agreeing on methodologies captures this idea rather neatly.

by individual researchers. The point here is that there is an irreducibly social group that makes judgements that need not reflect the judgements of its members.

2.5. THE POETRY DISCUSSION GROUP

To relate the above back with Gilbert's ontological maximalism and clarify this section's claim, consider Wilholt's (2016) conclusion that the implicit value judgements embedded in methodological standards are binding on a community's researchers "in the sense that they have to act as if they endorse them when they perform certain research-related activities" (230).⁶ The researchers are prepared to believe *X* or enact *X* in the way that the MEG does. This is precisely Gilbert's conclusion in her work on joint action theory. Joint commitment, as introduced earlier, requires that each individual do what they can "to emulate, as far as possible, a single body that *Xs*" (Gilbert, 2013: 176). Gilbert provides an example of a group believing in a way that needn't replicate in its members' beliefs.

⁶ Value judgements are implied by decisions to implement methods that are prone to either false positives or false negatives. Consider the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic. For the purpose of tracking the epidemiological evolution of the virus, tests were created to identify whether or not people were carriers of the virus. Unfortunately, such tests cannot be infallible. There is a chance that any one test shows either that the patient has the virus when they do not – a false positive – or that the patient does not have the virus when they effectively do – a false negative. In the context of the pandemic, and given certain government policies, a positive test could mean having to quarantine for a period of time. In the case where there are many positive cases, an economic contraction might follow because people can't make it to work. Conversely, negative tests allow individuals to continue working in-person but risk spreading the virus further. Given that the test cannot be 100% accurate, epidemiologists must decide how to treat data resulting from these tests. Should they allow a wider or smaller margin of error that allows for more false negatives or for more false positives? The trade-off is, by this brief outline, between the economy or livelihoods on the one hand, and morbidity or deaths on the other. This is not an easy decision, but social conventions in scientific practice help researchers bypass such complex conundrums: epidemiologists can settle for whatever p-value is considered acceptable.

In “the case of the poetry discussion group” (Gilbert, 1987: 190-194), we are asked to consider how such a group holds its meetings. To start, a poem is read out. Afterwards, group members can comment on the reading, offering suggestions and solving any opposing views through discussion. A preferred reading eventually emerges. The discussion finally ends and the poem is read out once again, this time in line with the suggestions from the discussion. At this point, it is “natural” for members of the discussion group to make claims such as “we found the final line quite moving” (*ibid.*: 190).⁷ The group, as a whole, is ascribed a belief in such utterances. This ascription is adequate on the basis that all or most members decided to let the final reading “stand” as that of the group. As an individual, there is no need to accept the final reading, but to be prepared to participate in the group’s acceptance of that reading.

Using Dang’s nomenclature and returning to MEGs, the poetry discussion group shows that we cannot ask each member of a MEG to believe in every R that sustains some scientific output P . With all this, I take it that MEGs are not reducible to their constitutive researchers and their philosophical study requires a Gilbertian account of their ontological status.

3. CHALLENGING ONTOLOGICAL MAXIMALISM

In this section, I argue that ontological maximalism does not provide a sufficiently detailed account of MEGs. Firstly, I briefly survey the academic context in which MEGs operate. I describe how a culture of “publish-or-perish” is promoted by academic incentives. This culture emphasises the importance of individualistic goals in MEGs, undermining the ontologically maximalist account provided thus far. Secondly, I introduce two challenges that MEGs face due to the identified individualistic incentives. This will reinforce the need for greater detail in philosophical accounts of MEGs.

3.1. ACADEMIC NORMS

⁷ Given my null experience in poetry discussion groups, I assume Gilbert’s claims about what is “natural” to conclude with are sufficient for the present purposes.

I will speak of “academic norms” to refer to conventions that proliferate across academic institutions. We have already seen how social conventions that shape scientific inquiry render MEGs irreducibly social. However, academic norms bring our attention to individualistic concerns, which ontological maximalism disregards. This section introduces two interrelated factors that constitute academic norms: (i) the reward structure and (ii) the peer review process. Whilst I do not intend to provide an exhaustive account of academic norms, it will be shown that these two norms feed into what is commonly denoted the “publish-or-perish” culture.

The reward system in academia shapes how individual researchers decide on the projects to pursue and the areas to train in. This is called the *credit economy in science* (Zollman, 2018). The credit economy in science emphasises the desire that scientists have to receive credit. Credit-seeking in science means prioritising one’s job-security and career prospects when conducting research. Credit here refers to the “prestige” that comes with being published in widely-read academic journals and being cited in other authors. These publications and citations then signal one’s aptitude as a scientist to peers in their field. This perceived aptitude then increases the likelihood of a scientist gaining further funding opportunities and having access to higher-status jobs. As Huebner & Bright (2020) explain, these factors build on each other and stabilise over time, confirming the prestigious standing the scientist has within their scientific community.

The *peer review system* also influences the decisions of individual researchers. Peer review in academia is a quality-assessment process. In seeking to publish a paper, a researcher must first identify an appropriate academic journal. As well as the journal being of some prestige, it must publish papers of the pertinent field. Indeed, publications are made in increasingly specialised academic journals (Zemsky., 1998). The credit economy incentivises publications in academic journals that specialise in the field one wants to succeed in. Meanwhile, these journals have peer reviewers with the necessary knowledge to assess the quality of papers submitted for publication.

Taken together, the above features form what is commonly known as the culture of “publish-or-perish”. It promotes the pursuit of credit, increased specialisation and high levels of productivity, amongst other things. This culture is deemed pervasive in academia and is arguably problematic for scientific integrity (Fanelli, 2010; Anderson et al., 2013; Heesen & Bright, 2020). Crucially, academic norms influence the activities of individual researchers. This complicates the account I have so far provided, as I have spoken of ontologically irreducible

groups. In what follows, I elaborate on why academic norms necessitate a more individualistic account of MEGs by describing how two challenges are particularly salient in the case of MEGs.

3.2. AGAINST MEGS

In this section, I spell out how the “publish-or-perish” culture plays a critical role in our understanding of MEGs. I argue that MEGs are challenged by at least two problems. First, I describe what Lee (2020) calls the “reference class problem for credit valuation in science”. This will clarify practical aspects of the reward structures and peer review system discussed in the previous section. Second, I introduce the “breadth-specialisation trade-off” discussed by Poteete et al. (2010). Both challenges necessitate an individualistic account of MEGs, which I provide in the subsequent section.

A critical question that MEGs face relates with how different disciplines evaluate scientific outputs and give credit. This is what Lee (2020) calls the *reference class problem for credit valuation in science* (RCP, hereafter). The RCP arises when a researcher belongs to different communities that disagree on how to evaluate research outputs. Lee provides three examples of where this can happen. Firstly, there is the case of researchers working within subdisciplines. Lee describes the rise of solid state physics as a subdiscipline of applied physics, which in turn is nested within physics (*ibid.*: 1029). Each community will have different ways of evaluating work in physics. An individual researcher in solid state physics, then, can be credited according to different metrics, depending on how broadly the community of valuation is defined. Secondly, the RCP arises when interdisciplinary research is published in interdisciplinary journals like *Science* or *Nature*. As Lee asks: “which reference class would be most relevant in evaluating the value of the interdisciplinary project (and why)?” (*ibid.*). Thirdly, there is the case where an academic, seeking promotion within their faculty department, must appeal to a decision-making panel with diverging preferences. They might disagree on the rankings they want to see the department do well on. These rankings, in turn, credit departments on the basis of publications in different academic journals. The academic faces the RCP and has to choose what venues to publish in on this basis.

These three examples of RCP are straightforwardly at play in MEGs. Firstly, the RCP is even more saliently present where epistemic boundaries are more clearly delineated. After all, Applied Physics and solid state physics are still relatively similar to each other as one is a subset of the other. Meanwhile, working within a MEG means networking with more diverse fields. Secondly, the question of how MEGs’ academic outputs are evaluated

clearly reflects Lee's concern with evaluating interdisciplinary work according to different disciplines' standards.

Thirdly, the pressures to impress different parties are present for each member of a MEG.

One illustration of the RCP for MEGs can be found at the final stages of a research project. Consider that, when a project is coming to an end, the research team will seek to publish their work. At this point, the group members will voice different opinions as to where the work is published – if they hadn't already. In our example, both the team of classicists and the team of computational scientists will have different preferences as to where the work is published and how findings are communicated.

There is a second challenge that is particularly relevant to MEGs. Poteete et al. (2009) identify a trade-off between breadth of knowledge and specialist training (the "trade-off problem", hereafter). The problem is simply that one cannot strive for both breadth of knowledge *and* specialisation. For MEGs to succeed, we would expect researchers to be able to acquire breadth of knowledge. This would allow researchers to engage with the diverse methodologies and disciplines that come together in MEGs. However, academic norms simply do not facilitate this. On the one hand, the academic incentives system rewards speed of publication. However, MEGs require activities that are extremely time-consuming. For example, researchers in MEGs might need to collect data from different sources, explore new bodies of literature and employ diverse methodologies. In practice, researchers are reluctant to do this sort of work (Heesen, 2018; Poteete et al., 2010: 406). On the other hand, recall that the peer review process encourages the publication of papers in highly specialised journals. This is reinforced by the specialisation of reviewers who are, themselves, sceptical before methodologies that are from other disciplines. Evidence shows that there is simply a lack of capacity to address multidisciplinary research through the traditional peer review system (McLeish & Strang, 2016).

With all this, it seems advisable that researchers do *not* work in MEGs. And yet the value of MEGs addressing interdisciplinary topics continues to be acknowledged by funding bodies (Resnick, 2011). This value is also intuitive given what's been discussed on the social epistemology of science. I take this conflict to be a defining feature of MEGs. Whilst MEGs are invaluable for the progress of modern scientific knowledge, academic norms pose challenges to researchers to thrive in MEGs.

4. BRATMANIAN MEGS

The two challenges for understanding MEGs by ontological maximalism discussed above are the reference group problem (RCP) and the trade-off problem. These are only two such challenges and need not be considered exhaustive. Crucially, I take these challenges to be a defining feature of MEGs in the context of academia. These challenges result from academic norms shaping individualistic desires in researchers, who partake in the credit economy of science. This is problematic for the account provided so far. Indeed, how do we defend that MEGs are ontologically maximal when their context encourages individualistic desires in their members? Gilbert's conditions for ontological maximalism – speaking in terms of *we** and sharing in the common knowledge of every other member's joint commitment – do not *prima facie* account for the credit economy of science. On the one hand, academic norms seem to encourage researchers to speak in terms of “I”. On the other hand, it is difficult to imagine members of MEGs showing “joint commitment” to methodological standards they do not all understand. After all, they are incentivised to specialise in narrow disciplines.

To account for these challenges in MEGs, I suggest stepping away from Gilbert's ontological maximalism and drawing on Michael Bratman's more individualistic account of joint action. Bratman's approach is to propose a planning theory of action that describes the mental states of individuals who partake in joint action. However, I will not discard the arguments provided thus far outright. Wilholt and Dang both argue convincingly for the ontological maximalism of MEGs, and do so from rather different angles. Hence, I will draw on Bratman's account to help make sense of MEGs as groups that *overcome* the aforementioned challenges.⁸

In what follows, I first outline Bratman's individualistic account of joint action. It will turn out his conclusions explain away potential divergences amongst group members' plans. I introduce his notion of “social glue” and then introduce the three norms that constitute this “social glue”: *social agglomeration*, *social consistency* and *coherence*, and *social stability*. I finally argue that these face limitations in the case of MEGs.

4.1. BRATMAN

⁸ This idea rests on an optimistic assumption: MEGs are here to stay and, whilst they are partly characterised by the challenges academia poses, they should be defined by their endeavours to surmount such problems.

Bratman (1993) provides an individualistic account of social groups, whereby each individual of a group has an intention of the form “I intend that we *J*”. Each fellow group member is aware of everybody else having this intention. Much like in Gilbert’s account, there is a role to be played by common knowledge. However, the “collectivist” aspect of Gilbert’s account is lost. For Bratman (2007), irreducibly social intentions do not exist. In the case of the poetry discussion group, Bratman would not see the group as a plural subject that “thinks” differently to its members. Rather, Bratman’s account takes individuals’ mental states to provide sufficient conditions for *shared intentionality*. Thus, he develops a “planning theory” that focuses on individual intentions.

By Bratman’s (2014) “planning theory”, intentions go beyond immediate actions. Intentions play an organising-coordinating role, whereby one conceives of both (i) complex objectives and (ii) the cross-temporal preliminary steps that are needed to reach these objectives. Bratman calls these “plans” and “sub-plans”, respectively. An example can help illustrate this point.

Consider the action of two individuals jointly painting a house. In such a case, *intentions* relate with effectively painting the house. Both participants in the joint action share this intention “that we *J*”. However, each individual’s intention may be constituted by different plans (e.g.: to paint one half of the house) and sub-plans (e.g.: to paint the bottom half of that section first).

Bratman does not consider divergent plans and sub-plans problematic so long as the intentions are *rational*; so long as they adhere to “norms of individual intention rationality” (*ibid.*: 33). It is beyond the scope of this essay to study whether researchers in MEGs are rational in Bratman’s sense, but we have already seen how academic norms can lead to researchers’ plans not aligning. Then, what is interesting from Bratman is his explanation of shared intentionality given his individualistic planning theory.

Bratman suggests a “glue that binds team members together” (Cohen et al., 1997: 2). This “social glue” (Bratman, 2014: 87) is constituted by three *social rationality norms*: social agglomeration, social consistency and coherence, and social stability.⁹ In what follows, I introduce each, and suggest how they might apply in the case

⁹ These norms are not to be mistaken with the academic norms described earlier on.

of MEGs. I argue that they are informative to the case of MEGs, but further precision is required to explain MEGs more adequately.

4.2. SOCIAL AGGLOMERATION IN MEGS

A useful distinction of Bratman's is between intentions – as introduced above – and *goals*. Goals are broader than intentions, but they can also enter into conflict. Bratman reintroduces the example of painting a house to make this distinction clear (Bratman, 2014: 29).

When jointly painting a house with somebody else, Bratman explains, one's intentions relate with painting the house. Both participants in the joint action share the intention to paint the house together. However, the goals of either party needn't be consistent. These are longer-term than intentions. For example, one might want to paint the house to later sell it for a profit, whilst the other wishes to paint the house to later donate it to the historical conservation society. Bratman characterises these goals as non-intentional (*ibid.*).

The distinction helps understand *social agglomeration*, the agglomeration of individuals' *intentions* into a larger social plan. Much like individuals' intentions, this social plan is constituted by their plans and sub-plans. The difference now is that their independent plans and sub-plans must interlock. This is the process of social agglomeration, and it poses a constraint on individuals' plans. In short, if individuals share intentions, they must configure their plans and sub-plans in such a way that they mesh with one another's and are, ultimately, conducive to the shared intention.

In the meantime, *goals* needn't mesh or agglomerate in this way. Individuals' goals can be set aside as plans and sub-plans are guided by deliberating on how to best achieve shared intentions. This mitigates some of the concerns we have in MEGs.

One might join a MEG for different reasons depending on their career stage, for instance. For a principal investigator who leads a MEG, it may be an opportunity to impress their promotion committee. For an early-career researcher on their first postdoctoral contract, working in a MEG can give them exposure to different practices across different disciplines and help them decide where to specialise next. Another example regards decisions about where to publish a paper or what conference to attend. These are diverging goals that needn't

detract from our successfully jointly working in a MEG. Bratman argues we might proceed with some joint action now and leave such decisions for later.

4.3. SOCIAL CONSISTENCY AND COHERENCE IN MEGS

Social consistency and coherence relate to shared “beliefs about matters of possibility and effectiveness” (Bratman, 2014: 30). Holding the shared intention in place, Bratman argues that group members must share notions of what plans and sub-plans, and what interactions between these are possible and effective to attain shared intentions. He calls these shared beliefs *background assumptions*. For example, disagreeing on what colour to paint a house is an inconsistency in background assumptions.

Bratman focuses on cases where “background assumptions” are consistent. This would be problematic for us, as MEGs do not share methodological standards.¹⁰ However, Bratman provides a solution to account for social groups that are not “consistent and coherent”. He introduces “deliberations” and “shared policies”. Arguably, Bratman does not engage with these questions very deeply.¹¹ After all, Bratman seeks an ontological account of social groups. Meanwhile, the question of deliberation falls into the camp of social epistemology.

4.4. SOCIAL STABILITY IN MEGS

Social stability refers to constancy throughout time. Bratman (2014) describes it as a sort of “snowball effect: once we are embarked on our shared activity, there will frequently be new reasons to continue” (90). These new

¹⁰ Although Bratman’s *background assumptions* are not identical to *methodological standards*, footnote 8 showed how *value judgements* are informed by methodological standards. I do not see the need to rehearse the further shift from *value judgements* to *background assumptions*.

¹¹ Bratman only drops the assumption of consistent background assumptions until the final chapter of his monograph (*ibid.*: §7), almost as an afterthought. This is one reason why something additional to Bratman’s social rationality norms is necessary in the case of MEGs.

reasons amount to the continued desire to successfully complete one's plans. Individualistic – rather than social – continued desires are what allow for stability. They also mean seeking that our sub-plans mesh and interrelate in an optimal way for our plans to be met. The snowball effect becomes social when we acknowledge the need for meshing our own sub-plans with those of others.

Social stability has a diachronic element that is well captured by the snowball analogy. Stability increases as a group works together. However, divergent sets of plans – e.g.: those of computer scientists and historians – can seem *prima facie* incompatible. There is still a question as to how members of an epistemically diverse MEG can go from (a) acknowledging the need to mesh sub-plans, to (b) effectively meshing sub-plans each member can't fully cognise. Once again, Bratman turns to *deliberations* to fill in these gaps.

4.5. MOTIVATING A SOLUTION

We have seen that social agglomeration, social consistency and coherence, and social stability constitute the “social glue” that helps individuals act in accordance with shared intentions. However, Bratman acknowledges that sufficiently divergent background assumptions can mean individuals' plans and sub-plans do not mesh in the intended way. This significant divergence in background assumptions reflects a key feature of MEGs: not sharing methodological standards. Hence, we need something additional to explicate the success of MEGs. I will argue that epistemic trust as value can effectively fill this gap and account for how MEGs can thrive.

Epistemic trust, recall, is about trusting in the reliability of other scientists' work. In the case of MEGs, we have seen that epistemic trust is ascribed to MEGs *qua* groups. What I suggest in the following section is that epistemic trust constitutes a mechanism that promotes Bratman's social rationality norms in the context of MEGs. The epistemic trust I argue for will itself rest on *social epistemic humility*.

5. OVERCOMING THE CHALLENGES

We have so far established that MEGs can be conceived of as plural agents. This is in light of Wilholt's notion of epistemic trust: scientists place trust in scientific groups by virtue of their peers adhering to academic norms

and the methodological standards that allow them to succeed in their own fields. Dang's analysis helps make a further point: research groups ultimately make judgements that are not *prima facie* reducible to the judgements of their individual members. However, we have also seen some of the challenges that scientists in MEGs can face; namely, the RCP and the trade-off problem. I suggested employing Bratman's individualist framework to make sense of groups whose members are driven by clashing incentives. In this section, I argue for a notion of epistemic humility that can help towards overcoming disagreements that result from academic norms. *Social epistemic humility* will turn out to promote *individualistic epistemic trust* that serves as a social glue along with Bratman's social rationality norms.

5.1. DEFINING EPISTEMIC HUMILITY

Medina (2013) defines epistemic humility as “[involving]attitudes and habits conducive to the identification of cognitive lacunas” (43). He argues that epistemic humility is a virtue that improves knowledge-production processes by requiring that one qualifies their beliefs, identifies what they need to overcome cognitive limitations, and formulates questions to themselves and others. Consider the following minimalist example:

Sam and Taylor just shared a meal at a restaurant. They each ate different menu items and are now splitting the bill. A quick check through the bill is enough for Sam to think they have to pay £17, and for Taylor think they owe £14. However, it is a £33 bill, so the numbers don't add up ($17+14=31$). Taylor then inspects the bill more closely and concludes Sam's meal cost £19, not £17.

In this scenario, we can picture Sam being able to respond in one of three ways:

1. Sam profoundly disagrees with Taylor's conclusion and maintains the view that they owe £17 without further examining the bill; or
2. Sam wonders if they made a mistake and re-examines the bill more carefully; or
3. Sam accepts Taylor's conclusion uncritically.

The first amounts to the epistemic “vice” that opposes epistemic humility: *epistemic arrogance*. Briefly, this is “the thought of being in full cognitive control of reality” (*ibid.*: 41). Epistemic arrogance does not leave space for others' views to be considered seriously.

The second option is where we see epistemic humility in action. It might be the case that Sam is aware of their own limitations in doing mathematical calculations in their head, or perhaps they trust Taylor's calculus skills enough to know to check the numbers again. Epistemic humility is present due to this self-evaluation and re-evaluation of the evidence.

The third option exemplifies what Medina calls "pathological" humility; a humility that "undermines one's confidence and erodes one's character" (*ibid.*: 43). This clarifies a negative definition of epistemic humility: it is not about blindly granting others cognitive superiority. Dormandy (2020) has called this being "intellectually servile."

Thus, we have a positive and a negative definition for epistemic humility:

Positive definition: Epistemic humility is about taking the views of others seriously and re-examining one's own claims to identify and fill "cognitive lacunas".

Negative definition: Epistemic humility is neither about being "intellectually servile" nor epistemically arrogant.

5.2. SOCIAL EPISTEMIC HUMILITY

Having defined *epistemic humility*, I turn to its usefulness to promote epistemic trust *within* MEGs. I first identify a condition that renders epistemic humility a *social* entity. I then explain how the concept helps MEGs overcome the trade-off problem.

Epistemic humility promotes trust amongst members of MEGs. The link between epistemic humility and epistemic trust is not novel. Consider Dormandy's (2020) two-pronged argument. On the one hand, epistemic humility's function of identifying one's own cognitive lacunas can lead to seeking out the tools to fill them in. In other words, epistemic humility promotes self-improvement. This self-improvement, in turn, promotes one's own greater epistemic trustworthiness. We have already seen this idea in action: Sam identified their own cognitive limitations and sought a method to fill the gap; Sam went through the bill again, this time more carefully.

On the other hand, Dormandy argues that epistemic humility can inform individuals of their capacities to meet the expectations of those who invest epistemic trust in them. In our humdrum example, this would be the case if either Sam or Taylor was the only person with access to the bill. The other party would simply need to trust them. The person with sole custody of the bill would demonstrate epistemic humility by seeking out the tools that fill in the gaps for their own cognitive lacunas. They would do what is necessary to earn their counterpart's trust.

Dormandy clarifies how epistemic trust is promoted by epistemic humility. However, the example provided thus far has been purposefully minimalist. In the context to MEGs, what I have exemplified with "access to the bill" is not quite so simple. We need a more complex notion of epistemic humility that can account for some members within MEGs having access not to a bill, but to highly specialised knowledge. I suggest supplementing the positive and negative definitions of *epistemic humility* provided in §5.1. with the following condition:

Condition for social epistemic humility: What members of MEGs are humble about includes the intellectual lacunas of their domain of expertise.

With this, we can now test *social epistemic humility* on the challenges we identified for MEGs. I focus on the trade-off problem.

Recall Poteete et al.'s (2010) evidence-based argument for academic incentives to specialise in unique disciplines. Conversely, "the great investment required to master any single method [...] limits the number of methods in which any individual can be expected to gain and maintain competency" (20). This is what motivates the study of MEGs in the first place: multidisciplinary is required to tackle the big questions of our time, but their members do not share methodological standards. We have already identified that epistemic trust can be attributed to MEGs whose methodologies we needn't – as individuals – entirely grasp. The question now is: how do we promote that trust amongst members of MEGs who do not share methodological standards?

Social epistemic humility promotes acknowledging that there are intellectual lacunas in one's own domain. Meanwhile, the trade-off problem means accepting that one's epistemic standpoint impedes fully engaging with others' disciplines. Researchers are incentivised to specialise rather than develop a broad depth of knowledge.

Thus, epistemic trust is promoted by being humble about what one's own field can achieve. We must trust the judgements of researchers from other domains to aid where our own fields are limited.¹²

6. OBJECTIONS

In this final section, I respond to two objections: that social epistemic humility is too demanding a solution and that I promote a "pathological" kind of trust.

6.1. TOO DEMANDING

I have suggested that epistemic humility be held by individual researchers to overcome institutional challenges to MEGs. However, I did not try to solve the RCP. The solution may be both irrelevant and too demanding. Social epistemic humility was supposed to help MEGs develop trust *amongst their members*. But the RCP – which I did not try to solve through social epistemic humility – clearly points to systemic problems beyond the realm of any individual MEG. Recall that the RCP is about the difficulty of assigning credit to researchers who work across epistemic boundaries. The problem is rooted in credit being assigned from well-delineated disciplines. The RCP is not solved with social rationality norms, nor with social epistemic humility. It seems that, if the RCP is to be solved through social epistemic humility, then the solution is simply too demanding. It entails that everybody in the research ecosystem – from students to tenured professors and funding bodies – show epistemic humility when crediting researchers. This conclusion, the objection goes, is simply infeasible.

¹² It is worth emphasising, once again, that epistemic humility not become "pathological." This is important in the academic context where perceived "brilliance" can often mean struggling with "impostor syndrome", especially amongst early-career and female scholars (Muradoglu et al., 2021). Impostor syndrome is present where "someone is talented, and has turned her talent into externally recognised success, yet reasonably doubts herself" (Hawley, 2019: §V). Although it is beyond the scope of this paper to extend this discussion any further, consider that directing humility at one's field can help reduce self-doubt, insofar that it is one's field – not oneself – what is being critically evaluated.

I consider this a valid critique of the section introducing the RCP. One response is that the RCP served as a heuristic to understand the hostile environment in which researchers working within MEGs operate. To this effect, social epistemic humility needn't solve the RCP. Another response is that my claim is that social epistemic humility constitutes but one part of a possible solution to the RCP for MEGs. If anything, the objection points to the ambition of my suggestion: I deeply believe in the value of MEGs and the need for systemic change to allow them to flourish.

Furthermore, the infeasibility of "everyone showing social epistemic humility" is an empirical claim. Whilst it might be difficult to imagine everybody in the academic ecosystem following such a virtue, it requires empirical observation to claim that this is indeed too demanding. If anything, this aspect of the objection requires testing governance policies in academia that are informed by social epistemic humility. I would encourage such research to be conducted through the sociology of science.

6.2. "PATHOLOGICAL" TRUST

The mention of trust as the end goal for the success of MEGs raises a further objection. I seem to have suggested that new-formed MEGs, when drawing on the work of other research groups, need not critically evaluate that work. They can just assume it was done right because they behave in the expected manner. The suggestion that MEGs trust one another by virtue of acting in a way that accords with academic institutions is problematic. It seems I promote a "pathological" form of trust. There are two responses to this objection, each of which further clarify the role I grant to epistemic trust.

Firstly, consider the "efficiency argument" mentioned in §2.2.:

1. MEGs must draw on great deals of research from different research groups
2. Research groups have more than one member
3. Therefore, there are more researchers than research groups
4. Therefore, it is more efficient to trust entire groups rather than each of their individual members.

This clarifies the motivation for my notion of epistemic trust. Epistemic trust as attributed to entire research groups facilitates the advancement of science by not needing to trust in the work of each of their members. For

example, it is much more efficient to trust that CERN followed best practice when identifying the Higgs Boson in 2012, than seeking to trust each of the 5,154 researchers involved (Castelvecchi, 2015).

Secondly, I did not explicitly call for an “uncritical” trust. Medina’s framework is helpful here. To avoid some “pathological” epistemic trust, effort must be spent in attributing that trust. Recall Sam uncritically accepting that they owed £2 more than they’d initially thought. This was precisely not what epistemic humility is about. Conversely, epistemic trust is not about trusting other research groups simply because they followed some set of shared academic norms. Indeed, Wilholt implies there is effort in this process when saying one “invest[s] epistemic trust” (2013: 233; italics my own). It is not a mere deposit of trust or some automatic ascription. Trust must be earned by research groups. Partaking in shared academic norms is just one way to ascribe epistemic trust. I hope that social epistemic humility can constitute another method for identifying trustworthiness in MEGs.

7. CONCLUSION

This essay has sought to contribute to the philosophy of interdisciplinarity. In particular, I have provided a theoretical framework through which to study the ontology of MEGs by drawing on joint action theory. I have shown an ontologically maximalist account is compatible with findings in the philosophy of science. I have argued for this in two ways. Firstly, I demonstrated that MEGs are conceived of – by scientific communities – as ontologically distinct from their members. Wilholt (2016) provided the foundation for this argument, as research teams are trusted without needing to scrutinise the trustworthiness of their individual members. This reflects Gilbert’s notion of speaking of groups in terms of *we**: plural subjects exist such that they are irreducible to their individual members. Secondly, I argued for Gilbert’s notion of MEGs as making judgements *qua* plural subjects. This was facilitated by Dang’s (2019) account of research teams upholding conclusions that needn’t be reducible to their members’ own conclusions.¹³

¹³ Note that I have argued for a weak account of plural subjects. I maintained that MEGs can make value judgements that some of their members agree with, partly by virtue of their partaking in the same academic

My account of the nature of MEGs was considerate of their academic context. I provided a brief overview of institutional factors that influence the behaviour of researchers who might form MEGs. I argued that academic norms challenge the ontological maximalism I had introduced. I accommodated my account to these challenges by drawing on Bratman's individualistic framework for studying joint action. Bratman's social rationality norms were introduced as a "glue" to bring otherwise divergent plans into shared social plans. However, Bratman's theory assumed consistency across the members of groups. Meanwhile, this assumption is unattainable in MEGs; a key feature is that they do not share methodological standards.

To complement Bratman's social rationality norms, I argued for a social epistemic humility that promotes epistemic trust amongst epistemically diverse MEGs. In short, by acknowledging the limitations of one's own discipline, one is prompted to trust those of other disciplines to fill in the gaps. This is not to advocate for some "pathological" notion of humility or trust. Rather, this is about encouraging an environment where diverse viewpoints can be successfully brought together.

I have cited evidence that multidisciplinary is on the rise in research. I have also referenced observational data about the challenges the academic environment poses to MEGs. I have suggested academia is generally hostile to MEGs. More importantly, I have suggested social epistemic humility as a method to overcome these challenges. Nonetheless, this conclusion requires further study into the precise methods for implementing social epistemic trust in MEGs. I trust sociologists of science can adequately test my thesis.

norms. This is not as strong a claim that has been made elsewhere: that groups can make judgements that none of their members agree with (Dang & Bright, 2021; Bratman, 1992: 7, 2014: 147).

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